

Variable spontaneous activity patterns at night in a uniquely dedicated and stereotyped birdsong premotor brain region

L. Nathan Perkins, Sanne Moorman*

Author contributions:

S.M. conceived of the study; S.M. performed the calcium imaging during sleep; S.M. and L.N.P. conducted data analysis and contributed analysis code and methods; S.M. interpreted results and wrote the manuscript. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

*Corresponding author: s.moorman@rug.nl

Abstract

Sleep activity sometimes shows similarity to daytime neural patterns (replay). However, replay constitutes only a fraction of all sleep-related neural activity, thus the majority of sleep-related neural activity *differs* from daytime sequences. Since most neurons are active during more than one behavior, it cannot be discriminated if non-replay activity patterns match stochastic daytime experiences, so stem from non-task related activities, or are caused by sleep-specific neural activation patterns. A birdsong premotor brain region called HVC (used as a proper name) is crucially important for song production in zebra finches. Neural activity in this brain region is very stereotyped during singing. HVC premotor projection neurons have a uniquely song-specific role, i.e. they are not active during non-singing behaviors, and thus provide a unique opportunity to study whether non-replay activity relates to daytime behavior or not. Here, we used fluorescence microscopy in conjunction with a genetically encoded calcium indicator to record spontaneous activity patterns during nighttime sleep in premotor nucleus HVC in adult male zebra finches. We found that activity of HVC projection neurons was highly variable. Activity patterns were characterized by irregular epochs in which multiple neurons were active simultaneously or in non-repeated sequences. This shows that the birdsong premotor network behaves more variable during sleep than during singing. Inspired by earlier findings of increased changes in the neuronal network for song and behavioral song variability after sleep (drift), we suggest that noisy neural activation during sleep might inject variability into the extremely stereotyped network. As such, sleep might allow neural networks to alter synaptic strengths, promoting neural plasticity. Such plasticity may in combination with redundant encoding eventually support long-term maintenance of stable behaviors.

Keywords: neural networks, birdsong, sleep, replay, drift, premotor

Introduction

During sleep in many animal species, neural activity in motor regions exhibits patterned or sequenced activity that is similar to the activation patterns seen during daytime behavior (reviewed in (Z. S. Chen & Wilson, 2023; Kaefer et al., 2022)). In addition to daytime-like, replayed patterns, sleep activity actually consists of more variable patterns for the majority of the night. The role of such variable patterns is unknown, though it is suggested that frequent spontaneous activity might be important for triggering replay patterns (Kaefer et al., 2022). However, it is unclear how non-replay activity during sleep relates to previous experiences—could it be replay of other events?—and/or how non-replay sleep activity affects behavioral performance on subsequent days.

In most animals and behaviors, the numerous possible daytime experiences make it difficult to know if nighttime activity patterns reflect earlier daytime patterns or not. In contrast, zebra finches are a songbird species in which males sing one, learned song with extremely little trial-to-trial variation (e.g., (Burke & Schmidt, 2020)). Premotor brain region called HVC (used as a proper name) produces extremely stereotyped patterns to produce song, and activity in its projection neurons was only found during singing behavior and sleep (Hahnloser et al., 2002).

HVC activation is necessary for adult song production in zebra finches. Lesions or perturbations of typical activity in HVC during song learning prevent the juvenile from learning to sing (Aronov et al., 2011; Roberts et al., 2012), and during adulthood disturb song performance (Basista et al., 2014; Long & Fee, 2008; Ölveczky et al., 2011; Poole et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2008; Williams et al., 1992). HVC projection neurons innervate the robust nucleus of the arcopallium (RA), which is the birdsong motor cortex (Burke & Schmidt, 2020). RA in turn projects to brainstem motor neurons that directly innervate vocal organ and respiration periphery (Burke & Schmidt, 2020). HVC neurons also project to the basal ganglia nucleus Area X, and the auditory nucleus Avalanche, both of which have a role in song plasticity (Trusel et al., 2025).

Neuronal activity in HVC is very stereotyped during singing: projection neurons burst sparsely, precisely aligned to an exact time point in song (Hahnloser et al., 2002; Katlowitz et al., 2018; Liberti et al., 2016; Markowitz et al., 2015). Unlike typical mammalian premotor neurons, which are involved in encoding diverse movements, activity in HVC projection neurons is uniquely dedicated to the single song that zebra finches produce, and projection neurons hardly fire spontaneously during wakefulness (Hahnloser et al., 2006) or during other motor movements.

It has been observed that spontaneous neural activity occurs in the songbird motor pathway throughout sleep (e.g., (Crandall et al., 2007; Hahnloser et al., 2006; Moorman et al., 2015; Shank & Margoliash, 2009)), including replay of daytime song motor patterns (Chi et al., 2003; Dave & Margoliash, 2000; Elmaleh et al., 2021). HVC activity during sleep depends on inputs from the nucleus interface of the nidopallium (Nif; (Hahnloser & Fee, 2007)), but also from thalamic nucleus uvaeformis (Uva) and potentially other regions, since replay events were still detected in HVC after lesioning Nif (Elmaleh et al., 2021; Hahnloser et al., 2008). In turn, HVC activity is the main driver of bursting activity during sleep in the robust nucleus of the arcopallium (RA), the song motor area (Elmaleh et al., 2021; Hahnloser et al., 2006). However, similar to hippocampal replay, birdsong premotor replay in HVC and RA constitutes a fraction of all sleep-related neural activity, thus the majority of sleep-related neural activity is *not* replay.

It is unknown what non-replay types of activation patterns look like, and how they relate to daytime behavior. In hippocampal paradigms this is hard to study, since animals navigate all day in lots of ways. In contrast, the zebra finch premotor cortical region HVC is only involved in producing one specific song, generating a very specific and stereotyped neural pattern. Thus, we have a unique opportunity to approach this question by explorative spontaneous neuronal network activity during the night in the songbird HVC. Using fluorescence microscopy in conjunction with a genetically encoded calcium indicator, we recorded spontaneous activity patterns during sleep and compared them to typical calcium activity patterns recorded during daytime singing in adult male zebra finches.

Methods

Animals

All experiments were performed in accordance with protocols approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees at Boston University, the New York University Langone Medical Center, and MIT. Data were obtained from N=3 adult zebra finch males (> 120 d old) from in-lab breeding colonies. When recovering from surgeries and in between imaging sessions, birds were housed individually in soundproof boxes. Birds received food and water ad libitum and were on a LD 15:9 light regime. In some recordings, we had the birds on a reversed day-night cycle. To adjust their light schedule, we had changed the time for lights on and off by 1 hour per day, and kept the birds on the reversed cycle for a minimum of 2 weeks before the first recording session.

Surgery. Surgeries were conducted under isoflurane gas inhalation anesthesia (3-4% isoflurane in oxygen induction, ~1-2% maintenance). The analgesic Meloxicam (0.5-1.0 mg/kg, IM) was injected at the start of the procedure and the animal was placed into a stereotaxic instrument. Bupivacaine (4 mg/kg) was injected subcutaneously into the scalp before an incision was made along the AP axis. A first surgery was performed to inject a retrograde tracer in a basal ganglia area downstream to HVC (area X), and attach a head plate to the skull allowing for future head fixation during imaging. Birds received ~50 nl injections of Dil (Invitrogen) dissolved to 5 mg/ml in dimethylformamide (Sigma) into area X bilaterally (5.8 mm anterior, 1.5 mm lateral of the bifurcation of the sagittal sinus, and 2.8 mm below the dura at a head angle of +20 degrees). A small steel plate (4.75 x 2.25 x 1.00 mm) with two threaded screw holes was embedded in the dental cement. Approximate coordinates for left and right HVC were marked on the skull (0.1 mm anterior, 2.3 mm lateral of the bifurcation of the sagittal sinus, at a head angle of +65 degrees).

Calcium indicator. A minimum of 1 week later we performed a second surgery to make a cranial window above HVC. We made bilateral craniotomies of 3–4 mm in diameter. Care was taken to minimize bleeding of the dura surface. After skull removal we used a custom pulled glass pipette for viral injections. For viral delivery, we use the genetically encoded calcium indicator GCaMP6f (T.-W. Chen et al., 2013) delivered by high titer lentiviruses (Markowitz et al., 2015; Scott & Lois, 2005). Birds received ~4 x ~250 nL injections of lentivirus packaged with GcAMP6f under a Rous sarcoma virus (RSV) promoter into HVC, to specifically label projection neurons. The boundaries of the nucleus were determined with a Dil retrograde tracer (c.f. (Poole et al., 2012)). Afterwards, a 3 mm coverglass (3 mm circular, #0, Corning 0211 borosilicate glass; Thermo Fisher Scientific) was placed on top and secured in place with optical-curing dental cement (Pentron Clinical Technologies).

Imaging sessions. We started imaging a minimum of 1 week after the second surgery to allow for high levels of GCaMP6f expression. Birds were taken from their cage at onset or within 1 hour after the lights had turned off (their nighttime). They were quickly transferred to a foam restraint to prevent the birds from flapping the wings. The head was fixed using the earlier attached head plate. Zebra finches do not typically sing in the dark, and our subjects never vocalized under the microscope. We applied ~20 µg of melatonin dissolved in Eucerin cream to the skin of the neck (c.f. (Derégnaucourt et al., 2012; Goymann et al., 2008)). In addition to keeping the bird in the dark, at their own nighttime, melatonin aided in stimulating sleep. An infrared camera was used to monitor the bird during the imaging session, where a video of the eye was used to infer if the bird was asleep: if the eye was closed stably and had been closed for > 30 seconds, we assumed the bird to be asleep (c.f. (Elmaleh et al., 2023)). We anecdotally noticed that HVC projection neurons did not show any activity when birds were awake (eye open, quiet wakefulness; confirming (Hahnloser et al., 2006)), further supporting our assumption that birds were sleeping during data acquisition. Randomly timed recordings of spontaneous neural calcium activity were made for 1-3 hours per night per bird, during the first half of the night, for 30 seconds – 2 minutes per video. Data acquisition was done with a digital CMOS camera (Hamamatsu Photonics K.K. ORCA-flash 4.0 V2, cooled) using a frame rate of 30 Hz.

Preprocessing of videos. Neuroanatomical organization in birds is in clusters, rather than layers. This means that cells visible under the lens are at different depths. Also, viral expression in birds is less effective than in mice, so labeling is generally sparser (c.f. (Heston & White, 2017; Markowitz et al., 2015; Nimpf et al., 2024)). Fluorescent traces for most animals were collected over multiple nights of imaging, but the fields of view were not aligned. The view included a large part of HVC (620 x 642 µm). All offline analyses were performed using custom software written in MATLAB (similar to (Markowitz et al., 2015)). First, the raw imaging data was motion corrected using a previously published algorithm (Guizar-Sicairos & Fienup, 2008). We computed $\Delta F / F_0$, where the F_0 is the fifth

percentile of background fluorescence.

Spike detection. Regions of interest (ROIs) were then manually selected and converted into single cell fluorescence traces by taking the mean intensity of all pixels within a given ROI for each movie frame. We used threshold crossings (2 times the standard deviation) of normalized ROI traces to convert the signal to spikes. We recorded for a total of 60 min in 10 sessions.

ON epochs. Spikes were not randomly distributed over time, but seemed to occur in bouts of synchronous or sequences of network activity. Such epochs of frequent activity alternated with periods of very little activity. Activity events were defined as “ON epochs” if they were at least 2 frames long, had a minimum of 3 ROIs active simultaneously in at least 1 of the frames, and included a maximum of 10 consecutive, *inactive* frames (0.33 sec). Of such ON epochs we analyzed the durations, frequency and interval durations. ON epoch durations were highly variable; the median duration was 0.9 sec. Intervals between ON epochs had variable durations too, with a median of 3.5 sec, but over the total recordings, on average we detected an ON epoch every 6 sec.

Spatiotemporal pattern analysis. During daytime, HVC activation follows very predictable spatiotemporal patterns: cells are active at precise times during song (Hahnloser et al., 2002; Katlowitz et al., 2018; Liberti et al., 2016; Markowitz et al., 2015). If nighttime activity would follow these patterns, we should find many repeated patterns in our videos. To test for this, we compared preceding and following activity around spikes that were detected. We decided to select a subset of reliable ROIs per video by visual inspection; ROIs that contained one single clear neuronal shape that was in focus, and without neuropil contamination in the ROIs. This smaller selection of ROIs was used as “reference points” to analyze variability in activity preceding or following their calcium events. We selected time windows from 1 sec before to 1 sec after detected-spike onsets, and analyzed the whole field of view (including all pixels, so independent from the ROI map). We made a maximum projection image of these video fragments centered around the reference ROI’s spike onset, showing maximum fluorescence that was detected in all pixels. The pixels were pseudo-colored to indicate relative time with respect to the detected-spike.

Additionally, we made average images of 1-sec long spike-triggered videos, calculating average pixel intensities per frame across the 0.5 sec before and after reference ROI’s spike onsets, and subsequently plotting maximum projection images of the average videos. The rationale is that if calcium events have a temporal relationship to the ROI reference points, the related pixel fluorescence will average to higher values than other pixels that will show chance level brightness. We then counted the number of ROIs that show increased brightness in these average images.

Daytime neural activity analysis. To check if these methods were indeed capable of detecting repeated spatiotemporal patterns, we used these analyses on previously recorded videos during daytime singing (Liberti et al., 2016), but this time blinded to the audio data or song onset times. Singing HVC activity was recorded in different birds, so we could not conduct a within-subject comparison. However, singing-related stereotypy in HVC spatiotemporal patterning has been confirmed many times in literature, making it highly unlikely that our sleep subjects would not fit this pattern.

Results

HVC neurons during sleep cycled through multiple second-long active and inactive epochs. Neural activity in head-fixed, sleeping birds with GCaMP6f expressed in HVC projection neurons was characterized by moments in which multiple ROIs showed increased fluorescence (see example in [Supplementary Video 1](#)). We used a set of criteria (see methods) to detect these as “ON epochs” in our data and characterized them with descriptive statistics ([Figure 1](#)). Both ON epoch durations and their intervals had wide, unimodal, and non-normal distributions (N = 629 detected bursts). These could potentially be similar to “up states” or “avalanches”. Rodents’ cortical circuits exhibit periods of intense activity during slow wave sleep, known as “up states”, that involve spontaneous, temporally organized spiking activity (Navarro-Lobato & Genzel, 2019). Songbirds have rapid eye movement and slow wave sleep phases that are similar to mammals (Beckers & Rattenborg, 2015; Rattenborg & Martinez-Gonzalez, 2015), but we have not recorded EEG signals to determine sleep states, so whether or not ON epochs could resemble up states remains to be tested.

Neural activity during singing is stereotyped. We were interested in detecting spatiotemporal patterns in sleep data, but wanted to ensure that we would be able to detect structured, recurring patterns with a method that cannot be aligned to song, as HVC studies usually do. We turned to a previously recorded data set of HVC activity recorded during daytime singing behavior (Liberti et al., 2016). As previously described, neurons were active in a well-defined sequence, time-locked to singing behavior (Liberti et al., 2016), ([Supplementary Video 2](#)). However, to compare activity patterns with sleep, we did not use the conventional alignment to behavior. Instead, we selected several single ROI “reference points”. In these reference point ROIs, we detected all onsets (threshold crossings) and took the frames before and after the calcium onsets from all videos made during one recording session (see methods). From these frames, we analyzed the whole field of view to compare calcium events preceding or following the reference ROIs’ activity. We reasoned that if neurons are active in stereotyped sequences, this analysis should be able to discover those repeated patterns. However, the recordings were of diverse length, with non-standardized silent paddings before and after singing, and contained a variable number of songs, with natural trial-to-trial variations in specific bout structure that zebra finches have (Hyland Bruno & Tchernichovski, 2019). Thus, we wanted to check first if we could detect the typical extreme stereotypies. Indeed, regardless of which ROIs we selected as reference points, the resulting pseudo-colored maximum projection images were very similar across events ([Figure 2](#)). Thus, even with this analysis approach that was unaware of onset of singing behavior, we detected very stereotyped sequences of daytime HVC network activity.

Neural activity is not stereotyped, but noisy during sleep. Just like in the singing analysis, we again selected a subset of ROIs as “reference points” and compared activity in all pixels in the videos before and after the calcium onset in the reference points. As can be seen in the resulting pseudo-colored maximum projection images ([Figure 3](#)), fluorescence signals preceding or following reference ROIs’ activity were highly variable. ROIs had low probabilities to initiate ON epochs, and any ROIs could be co-active with any given other ROIs. A variable number and identity of ROIs were active before or after spikes were detected in the reference ROIs, sometimes there were more diffuse increases in neuropil fluorescence, and in some cases, there was hardly any other activity in the field of view. It was very striking that none of the spatiotemporal patterns was found more than once, indicating that structured, recurring patterns are rare enough that we have not detected them.

Comparison calcium events characteristics sleep versus singing. Next, we wanted to compare sleep and singing activity. To do this, we made averaged images from 1-sec fragments (see methods). If any ROI activity would be sequentially related to the selected reference points, there should be a higher average fluorescence in those ROIs than other parts in the field of view. However, during sleep, most pixels had no specific activity relative to the reference ROI ([Figure 4, top](#)). The lack of ROIs with precisely timed average fluorescence means that activity is averaged out, indicating the lack of any consistent patterns. We assessed the ratio of ROIs that were distinguishable in the averaged images, which was 0.11 for sleep (4 out of 37 ROIs that showed any activity in the spike-triggered 1-sec videos). In contrast, when we conducted the same analysis on the singing video fragments, we found that the majority of ROIs had consistent timing across the averaged images (ratio 0.92, 45 out of 49 ROIs) ([Figure 4, bottom](#)). In conclusion, this analysis shows that our recordings during nighttime contain variable activity patterns, while daytime singing activity is stereotyped.

Discussion

To study activity of HVC neurons during sleep and daytime singing, we used fluorescence microscopy in conjunction with a genetically encoded calcium indicator. We found that sleep-related activity of HVC neurons differs greatly from typical daytime singing, in that it was characterized by irregular activity epochs of multiple neurons with variable spatiotemporal patterns. The variability of activity patterns during sleep that we found was extremely apparent, which was different from typical singing-related activity during wakefulness, and thus we argue that our data are convincingly pointing to an important, noisy phenomenon of neural networks during sleep.

In HVC, interneurons are densely connected to projection neurons, and tightly control the timing of their daytime activity (Kosche et al., 2015; Markowitz et al., 2015). During sleep, interneuron activity has longer interspike intervals (Hahnloser et al., 2006) and thus allows for more liberal responses to birds’ own song playback (Chi et al., 2003; Nick & Konishi, 2001, 2005; Vallentin et al., 2016). This same principle may also enable more variable spontaneous activity of projection neurons during sleep. Noisy HVC activity during sleep could be a form

of birdsong exploration or “preplay” (Pfeiffer & Foster, 2013), meaning that some of the co-activations during sleep may generate new patterns in future song production.

Consistent with this hypothesis is the finding that higher multiunit firing rates in HVC during sleep correlated with larger overnight song changes (Crandall et al., 2007). A causal relationship with HVC activity is not shown, and another potential mechanism for overnight song changes is that the night is a period without vocal practice (Adam et al., 2023). Nonetheless, many studies have reported overnight increase in song variability and decrease in entropy variance, a spectral feature that indicates song complexity (Brudner et al., 2023; Crandall et al., 2007; Day et al., 2009; Derégnaucourt et al., 2005; Kollmorgen et al., 2020; Liberti et al., 2016).

Sleep induced song deterioration might seem detrimental to song performance, but instead it correlates positively with eventual song learning success (Brudner et al., 2023; Derégnaucourt et al., 2005). During the day, juveniles increase song complexity through a process of reinforcement learning, and the resulting performance at the end of the day is better than the end of the previous day (Brudner et al., 2023; Derégnaucourt et al., 2005). Indeed, morning singing triggered higher levels of Arc mRNA expression in Nif and RA of juvenile zebra finches than singing in the afternoon (Hayase & Wada, 2018). Arc is an immediate early gene that regulates synaptic plasticity; thus, these results could indicate that song practice after sleep-induced changes promotes plasticity, to ultimately support high-quality song learning.

An interesting hypothesis is that sleep changes to song are needed to find the ultimately best performance. Daytime reinforcement of the best songs of that day may select the “local maxima” of song performance, but those might not be the ultimate best motor patterns. When sleep generates more variability, it may allow the premotor circuit to explore more states and develop an optimal as well as robust performance (Faisal et al., 2008). Another hypothesis is that noisy activation during sleep enables neurons to drift into the song network—“fire together during sleep, wire together”. Zebra finches have high rates of neurogenesis in HVC, and newborn neurons become part of the song network over time (Pytte et al., 2012; Tokarev et al., 2016). Noisy neural activation during sleep might be key in incorporation of newborn neurons into the tightly-controlled song network.

In conclusion, we found variable patterns of activity during sleep in a birdsong premotor region that shows sparse, precise activity patterns during the day. Such variable co-activations during sleep may promote plasticity in the premotor network. Small increases in premotor plasticity may help to make the neural network underlying song production more robust (c.f. (Duffy et al., 2019)), or even predict novel future daytime patterns (c.f. (Pezzulo et al., 2021)). Reinforcement learning might shape which changes in the network are reinforced versus removed in the next morning. Thus, noisy network activity during sleep may eventually promote and support long-term maintenance of behavior, even if it is at the cost of a temporary reduction in behavioral stability.

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Figures & Legends

Figure 1. Epochs of increased activity during sleep as measured by calcium imaging. Many regions of interest (ROIs) spiked together interleaved by relative quiet periods (see also Supplementary Video 1). **A-D:** Four example one-minute-long recordings during sleep. In the top graphs the $\Delta F/F$ traces are plotted; colored lines indicate fluorescence traces in multiple ROIs in our field of view over HVC. Middle panels show the spikes that were extracted from these traces (rows correspond to traces above). We detected calcium events as increases in the level of fluorescence, and showed the onset times (threshold crossings) in raster plots. Bottom histograms depict the total count of ROIs that spiked in each frame. **E:** Left: Duration histogram for $N = 629$ detected ON epochs (in 3 birds, 10 nights, 62.9 min total recording time). Mean duration is 1.2 sec; median 0.9 sec. Right: Durations of intervals between ON epochs; mean duration is 5.7 sec; median 3.5 sec. Both durations have wide, unimodal, and non-normal distributions.

Figure 2. Neuronal activity during singing behavior shows highly stereotyped spatiotemporal patterns of activity. We selected one reference ROI (circled and indicated with arrow in image 1) and selected fragments of 1 sec before and after each spiking onset in the reference ROI from recordings during daytime singing (Liberti III et al., 2016). The graph on the left shows the spike trace in the reference ROI for 5 times it spiked. The maximum projection images on the right (numbered 1-5 correspondingly) are pseudo-colored to show the timing of activity in all pixels of the video fragments (color legend on bottom right). Image quality is a bit grainier and non-averaged fluorescence traces are noisier than in figure 3 because of the different microscope quality (sleep: epifluorescence table top microscope; singing: head-mounted, miniature microscopes). The recordings were of diverse lengths, with non-standardized silent periods before and after singing, and contained a variable number of motifs, with natural variations in bout structure. Importantly, we were blinded to song timing during the analysis. However, as becomes clear by comparing the 5 images, activity that precedes and follows spiking of the selected reference neuron during singing is highly stereotyped.

Figure 3. Calcium imaging reveals that neuronal spikes during sleep are preceded by noisy, non-stereotyped activity. Similar procedures as in figure 2. The different maximum projection images show unique spatiotemporal patterns around the activity of the reference ROI. For example, see image 1: the example cell that spiked is bright green, and there is some activity in ROIs around it that immediately precede or follow. In the next image, other activity follows (orange and red). As becomes clear by comparing all images, activity that precedes and follows spiking of this neuron during sleep is variable and non-stereotyped.

Figure 4. Comparison of average spatiotemporal patterns during sleep versus singing. From 4 reference ROI-triggered 1-sec fragments, we made average projection images and indicated ROIs with red and green circles. **Top:** During sleep, most pixels around the reference ROI had equal brightness, indicating a lack of any consistent patterns. Top left: 3 ROIs were distinguishable in the averaged images triggered by activity in cell #3, while in total 21 ROIs showed activity at some point during all 1 sec fragments. Top right: 1/16 ROIs was visible after averaging based on cell #17. **Bottom:** The same analysis during singing shows that the majority of ROIs had increased fluorescence (bottom left: 21/23 ROIs; bottom right: 24/26 ROIs). Thus, sleep activity patterns are variable, while daytime singing activity is stereotyped.